

Reframing Social Research in the Arctic: Humanizing and Indigenizing Pathways to Improve Research Quality and Sociocultural Relevance

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Abstract

This White Paper presents a reflection on processes and practices, including hidden and silenced issues, of conducting social research with Indigenous communities in the Arctic and describes key principles guiding this work and practical recommendations to achieve greater societal relevance and culturally grounded research practices. These principles include implementing "humanized" research procedures, prioritizing practically oriented research that addresses community needs, (w)holism in the social research framework, emphasizing personal storytelling and a voice-centered approach, employing the "two-eyed seeing," and ensuring research accuracy through participant feedback on the research team's interpretations, among others. The paper further discusses challenges in efforts to strengthen Arctic research methods and approaches.

Why Humanizing and Indigenizing Research Practice are Critical in the Arctic

The need to reframe Arctic social research to improve research quality and sociocultural relevance has become apparent in multiple studies identified and strived to overcome some of the key challenges that stem from the 'dehumanized' nature of social research that is exclusively equipped with Western research methods and relies on Western institution-driven regulations and expectations. These include research that is:

- **Objectified** (treating participants as "research subjects") (Bromley et al. 2015; Cochran et al. 2008; Smith 2012).

- **Decontextualized** (lacking historical and cultural background, or institutional contexts in which the data were generated for potential biases) (Holmes 2025).
- **Formalized** (nominal inclusion of Indigenous scholars or community partners to fulfill expectations in grant proposals; conducting research in formal “laboratory” settings, when the research process, particularly during interviews, does not necessarily prioritize the physical comfort and psychological well-being of research participants; requiring signed consent forms and cash receipts; giving out gift cards that may be inaccessible to use for rural residents in remote communities or may not be useful for all participants; requiring the use of unnecessarily complex registration processes for payments in university systems, etc.).
- **Extractive** (prioritizing research agenda over community interests; lacking reciprocity when data from communities goes to Western institutions with very limited to no return to communities; giving limited to no intellectual credit to communities; no fair compensation for data collected during interviews; no long-term engagement with communities) (Cochran 2008; Igwe et al. 2022; Godrie 2025).
- **Hierarchical** (hierarchy of knowledge systems by prioritizing Western research paradigms (Ewing 2022); hierarchical relationship and uneven power dynamics between researchers and study participants (“research subjects”) (Alatas 2025).
- **Non-equitable** (e.g., research questions and methods are defined by non-Indigenous researchers or knowledge-holders; Indigenous communities have little or no control over how the study results are interpreted; researchers benefit with funding, publications, and/or career advancements, while communities often face little or no meaningful improvements; interview or focus group participants are often compensated with gift cards that are inaccessible to residents of remote communities instead of cash compensation) (Kouritzin & Nakagawa 2018).
- **Language-biased** (relying on dominant languages, often lacking the capacity to fully grasp nuances of local Indigenous Knowledge) (Chiblow & Meighan 2022; Ksenofontov et al. 2025).
- **Western institution-driven** (research governed by institutional expectations, deadlines, strict funds distribution rules, and other processes, e.g., IRB requirements) (Wapau et al. 2022).

In recent years, a growing body of literature has examined approaches to transforming dominant Western research paradigms in social research, particularly through the incorporation of Indigenous Knowledge and methodologies through participatory research (Weber-Pillwax 2009; Nadeau et al. 2022). While a number of overarching principles, such as CARE (Collective

Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) (Taitingfong et al. 2024; Carroll et al. 2022, Carroll et al. 2020), have been articulated, many practical considerations and contextual nuances remain underexplored. To bridge some of the gaps, this White Paper presents findings from experiences conducting social research with Arctic Indigenous communities and offers insights into improving research quality and outcomes for communities.

Practical Implementation of Humanized Research: Principles and Procedures

The solutions on “humanizing” Arctic research in Indigenous communities and beyond, and to ensure that research is respectful and inclusive of Indigenous Knowledge, is ethically conducted, and addresses urgent community needs and priorities, in many aspects lies in Indigenization of research. This process includes Indigenization of research teams, methods, and timeframes, communication with research participants (Absolon 2010), co-production of data analysis, results interpretation and dissemination (Baldwin 2023; Denzin & Lincoln 2008; Fast & Kovach 2019; Kovach 2021; Rozanova-Smith et al. 2025), prioritization of practically-oriented research that addresses community needs (ICC 2022), emphasis on personal storytelling and a voice-centered approach (Kovach 2021; Martin & Miraboopa 2003), implementation of CARE principles (Taitingfong et al. 2024; Carroll et al. 2022), employment of the “two-eyed seeing” method (Bartlett 2012), integration of (w)holism into the social research conceptual framework, solicitation of participant and local Indigenous organizations feedback to ensure research accuracy (IASSA 2024; Quinless 2022), and promotion of local Indigenous languages (Charlene Apok, personal communication, 2022). Among the most important principles and procedures are the following:

- **Research responsive to community needs** (ICC 2022). The research goal, objectives, and questions should be relevant to community needs to ensure that the outcomes are practical, meaningful, and beneficial for addressing the specific challenges the community faces. It’s important to trust the expertise of local partners and community liaisons.
- **Meaningful Indigenization of research teams.** It is imperative to move beyond a purely formalistic approach to the involvement of Indigenous scholars that is driven primarily by grant proposal requirements and instead foster meaningful engagement at all stages of the project to support knowledge co-production. Additionally, Arctic Indigenous cultures are highly diverse. A good practice for Indigenizing research teams is, in addition to engaging senior Indigenous scholars who may or may not have meaningful connections to the partner communities, to include a community knowledge holders who can participate in project working meetings, contribute to recruitment and interview scheduling, and provide feedback on research procedures, local cultural

contexts and urgent community needs. Such Indigenization of the research team strengthens meaningful connections with partner communities while also supporting culturally grounded and community-relevant research.

- ***A suitable time frame selection for interviews*** (ICC 2022; Marquez 2022). Care should be taken to adjust community visits and interview schedules in accordance with Indigenous seasonal calendars and traditional subsistence activities (hunting, fishing, gathering, etc.), ceremonies, etc. Usually, most research activities are conducted during academic summer breaks and can cause additional disruptions to communities during the busy hunting/fishing/gathering season. For instance, In Alaska, to prevent the most inconvenience, community visits can be scheduled for November-beginning of December, in consultation with local communities.
- ***(W)holism in the social research framework*** (ICC 2022). Arctic social sciences grounded in Western methodology predominantly rely on deficit-based models, emphasizing the challenges and vulnerabilities of Arctic communities, particularly in remote areas. At the same time, a strength-based framing is highly important when conducting research with Indigenous communities (Eichelberger et al. 2022; Bullen et al. 2023; Aulandez et al. 2021). It allows to identify community strengths associated with adaptability, resourcefulness, Indigenous Peoples' empowerment and cultural stewardship, and their ability to elicit community solidarity (mainly in rural areas) that contribute to individual and community resilience. In addition, this approach allows us to better acknowledge and incorporate Indigenous Knowledge and cultural practices into the research analytical framework. A more comprehensive approach, integrating both deficit-based and strength-based models, would offer a more holistic understanding of the subject, aligning with Indigenous concepts of a "wholistic" worldview (Absolon 2010, p. 74). Incorporating elements of Indigenous research methods into this integrated framework is crucial for deepening our understanding of the complexity and interconnectedness of social issues, as well as for developing more balanced and effective solutions to community issues by considering multiple perspectives and ensuring that no significant aspect is overlooked.
- ***Indigenous multi-layered approach to social studies on health and well-being*** (ICC 2022). To the best possible degree, it is important for the researchers to incorporate Indigenous all-encompassing approach to health and well-being, "which encompasses the spiritual, emotional, mental, and physical elements of being, <while also acknowledging> past, present and future" (Absolon 2010, p.74), into a research conceptual framework.
- ***Humanizing interview procedures***. Attention should be given to creating a welcoming and safe conveniently located space that would be a private, quiet place with a relaxed and informal atmosphere where participants would feel comfortable and less intimidated,

so that they are more comfortable with open conversation. Special attention should be given to the details, including various seating options, ambient lights, comfortable room temperature. Project teams may also consider incorporating culturally meaningful elements, such as local Indigenous ivory carvings or a natural hide rug placed on the couch, which were appreciated by many of our study participants. Although it is usually recommended for focus groups format to provide coffee/tea and snacks for participants, adapting this practice to individual interviews is important as comfort food and refreshments not only appreciated by research participants but also may trigger a temporary feeling of calm and stress relief (Tomiya et al. 2011; Zellner et al. 2006) and “fuel a positive environment” (Absolon 2010, p.83).

Photo: Interview setting. COVID-GEA project.

- ***Open-ended questions that invite personal storytelling and are also practically oriented*** (Archibald 2008). The interview questions should be designed as open-ended questions to allow the engagement of participants in meaningful conversation and sharing through personal stories that “are born of connections within the world and are recounted relationally” (Kovach 2021, p. 158). Some questions might address purposeful Indigenous research that is “far-reaching” and “also about shaping policy and practice so as to benefit Indigenous lives” (Kovach 2021, p. 242).
- ***A voice-centered approach to interpretation and broader impact activities.*** It is important to include extensive quotes from the interviews in the paper to allow readers to directly engage with the participants' voices and to ensure that their experiences are conveyed in their own words, adding credibility to the research findings (Martin & Mirraboopa 2003, p. 213). It is also vital to center participant voices in broader impact activities, for example by organizing digital platforms for sharing community stories (COVID-GEA 2023), developing audio-visual exhibitions based on those stories (COVID-GEA 2024), and translating some interview quotes into local Indigenous languages (COVID-GEA 2025).
- ***Research verification through feedback solicitation, knowledge-sharing, and reporting back.*** As part of the initial clarification and verification of what participants said during interviews (Mero-Jaffe 2011), it is considered good practice for researchers to share a summary of the interview information and its preliminary interpretation with participants upon completion of each interview. This allows for immediate feedback and the correction of any statements requiring more accurate interpretation, as well as preventing misunderstandings. Furthermore, preliminary study findings should be disseminated to all research participants who have email accounts and access to the Internet. This distribution aims to facilitate knowledge sharing, ensure the accuracy of interpretations, and allow participants to contribute feedback, thereby enhancing the final version of manuscripts prepared for publication (ICC 2022; Quinless 2022, p. 115). Notably, the time that research participants spend reviewing preliminary findings and reporting back should be compensated.
- ***Indigenous communities' control over research, data collection, and analysis processes*** (ICC 2022; IASSA 2024) through community approvals, partnerships, Free, Prior, and Informed Consent, and formal agreements such as Memoranda of Understanding and Memoranda of Agreement that clearly specify roles and responsibilities in joint projects, including community participation in research process, funding allocation, data ownership, and results dissemination. For instance, in Alaska, approval is required from the regional Institutional Review Board entity and local Tribal Research Review commissions.

- **A “two-eyed seeing” approach implementation.** When working together, Indigenous and non-Indigenous researchers use “one eye with the strengths of Indigenous knowledges and ways of knowing” and “the other eye with the strengths of Western knowledges and way of knowing and to using both these eyes together, for the benefit of all” (Bartlett 2012, p. 335). For example, during the qualitative analysis of interview data, the project team may use shared software for thematic coding and content and discourse annotation, as a mechanism for Indigenous and non-Indigenous researchers to collaborate simultaneously in real time. To ensure the trustworthiness of the results, researchers also independently review all the data and discuss their findings to include a “two-eyed seeing” approach that brings together Indigenous and non-Indigenous perspectives.
- **Safety-first approach.** Given the elevated risks and serious consequences associated with viral outbreaks in remote communities, researchers should take measures to protect community members. The preparation for in-person interviews should include up-to-date vaccination, COVID-19 home testing in case of risks of virus exposure, maintaining physical distance, and keeping windows open prior to interviews (and if it’s convenient, during the meeting).
- **Approval of data dissemination from the local Indigenous entity** (ICC 2022). The approval for use of the research materials (including quotes from the interviews) for publication and presentation at the conferences should be obtained from the relevant partner community organization or local ethics board (for instance, in the Nome region, the Norton Sound Health Corporation Research Ethics and Review Board).
- **Contribution to Indigenous languages vitality.** To ensure the research is contributing to Indigenous language revitalization, and with participants’ consent, significant study findings and quotations from the interviews can be translated into local Indigenous languages in both written and oral (video and/or audio) formats (Charlene Apok, personal communication, 2022) and published on project websites and media platforms. For instance, the COVID-GEA Project translated selected materials into Iñupiaq, a widely used language in the Nome area. Notably, the translations were done by Alaska Language Panel in accordance with Alaska Native Language Translation Protocols (COVID-GEA 2025).

Challenges to Implementing of Humanized Research Approaches

While theoretical frameworks and best practices in participatory research and the Indigenization of research methods are well documented, a recently emerging body of literature emphasizes the challenges of their implementation. In contribution to ongoing academic discussions (for

instance, Nadeau 2022; Beacock 2025; Moosavi 2025), this paper also presents some of these challenges that are particularly relevant to interview-based social research in the Arctic:

- ***Meaningful participant engagement in interview-based studies is time- and effort-intensive.*** Reaching out to research participants after interviews to share preliminary findings and solicit feedback for corrections, missing points, and further insights requires substantial time and additional resources, including funds to compensate participants for their further contributions. Incorporating this feedback may also require significant revisions to certain sections of draft materials prepared for publication. This process affects both researchers and study participants, as the latter devote time to reviewing preliminary findings and preparing informed feedback. Without compensation for these participants' efforts, such practices may be considered unethical.
- ***Inclusive authorship practices may clash with IRB protocols.*** Recognizing research participants' contributions in the form of authorship might cause violation of the IRB protocols by presenting possible risks to privacy and personal data protection, as well as Indigenous community data sovereignty.
- ***Traditional Western-based journals may be reluctant to publish research that incorporates Indigenous methodologies,*** Indigenous Knowledge systems, or Indigenous epistemological narratives, on the grounds that such contributions are outside conventional scientific frameworks.
- ***Extensive use of interview quotations may result in lengthy manuscripts and complicate the review and publication process.*** Despite most journals being electronic, a limited number of journals allow extended manuscript lengths. Lengthy papers also tend to complicate and prolong the peer-review process.
- ***The need for real-time collaborative work among researchers.*** Particularly critical for the "two-eyed seeing" approach, researchers have to allocate time to code interviews together in real time, which often requires taking into account time zone differences and the need to establish schedules that work for everyone.
- ***Burnout among researchers.*** This is sometimes overlooked that researchers are human beings, not machines that collect and analyze data. In Arctic community-based studies, researchers often engage with emotionally challenging contexts while conducting in-depth interviews and analyzing interview-based data, all while striving to adhere to both Western academic regulatory frameworks and Indigenous ethical protocols. Despite the increasingly real risk of burnout, this topic is largely absent from academic discussion.
- ***Limitations of project budgets that address only direct research needs and administrative charges while overlooking community members and researchers***

themselves. Western institution-driven regulations often impose budgetary constraints that limit opportunities for more meaningful engagement with communities, such as providing comfortable interview spaces, refreshments (e.g., coffee, snacks), informational materials about the project and related web resources, fair cash compensation for participants' contributions, and small tokens of appreciation. In some cases, research conducted in Arctic remote communities requires researchers to purchase equipment such as cold- and water-resistant clothing, sleeping bags, etc. These costs are typically classified as personal expenses and are not reimbursed, creating financial pressure on researchers, especially those at early career stages. Some institutions also provide per diem allowances that may be insufficient in certain Arctic locations.

- **Broader impact activities often require stepping beyond established research comfort zones.** Achieving meaningful broader impacts requires researchers to adopt digital solutions, including website development, the use of photovoice method and the creation of digital platforms for community voices, the production and dissemination of explainer videos, as well as the organization of exhibitions at conference venues and in community public spaces, among other outreach efforts. Researchers are also encouraged to communicate study findings to decision-makers and translate results into policy-relevant recommendations and prepare practically oriented publications adapted for community needs (policy roadmaps, community development plans, etc.).
- **Growing community expectations of long-term and more meaningful collaboration.** To avoid “parachute research” practices, researchers are encouraged to develop immersive, relationship-based engagement with partner communities by not only staying there for extended periods during fieldwork but also visiting communities before a project formally begins (for instance, discussions during the NNA meetings in 2023-2025). This may result in significant stress for researchers, as for many of them it is impossible to implement due to their institutional responsibilities, family commitments, as well as budgetary constraints.
- **Unfulfilled expectations of positive changes in communities.** Outcomes of participating in research are not always tangible or immediately beneficial for communities and might lead to research fatigue and frustration.
- **One-way sharing of lived experiences.** It is common practice for social scientists to learn about the communities they visit, whereas it is far less common for them to share information about their own home communities, personal lives, academic work, or the professional challenges they face. This practice does not enrich Arctic communities with valuable knowledge that could be gained from researchers lived experiences.

Conclusions

While significant advances have been made in the Indigenization and humanizing of Arctic research over the past several decades, a considerable disconnect persists between declared goals and priorities of social science research based on strong community engagement, transdisciplinarity and knowledge co-production, and advancement of research methodologies within the Western science tradition and institutional practices. Many of methodological issues remain unaddressed, hidden, or even concealed, lacking acknowledgement and reflection by researchers. Although many innovative methods of making research more humanized and socioculturally relevant have been introduced, their description, adoption, and assessment in academic literature is strikingly scarce.

In light of the 5th International Polar Year (IPY) upcoming in 2032-33 and the new era of Polar research, there is a renewed and urgent need to elevate the discussion focused on Arctic research methodologies and ensure implementation of humanizing and Indigenizing principles across all domains and stages of the research process. The incorporation of these innovative approaches, along with addressing implementation challenges, under the auspices of IPY, International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA), UArctic, Arctic Observing Summit (AOS), and other relevant organizations and initiatives will meaningfully contribute to the development of new research methodologies and increase the significance of Arctic research at the global level.

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